

ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING FINANCIAL STABILITY IN STATE-OWNED ENTERPRISES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20523730>

Abstract. *In this article, the financial stability of state-owned enterprises was assessed using the example of Regional Electric Networks JSC. The study analyzed liquidity, debt, return on assets, and enterprise size indicators based on 28 quarterly observations from Q2 2019 to Q1 2026. To assess financial stability, the FS index was formed based on normalized indicators and its dynamics over time were assessed using the Newey–West model. The results showed that the FS index increased by an average of 0.006 units per quarter and this increase was statistically significant. According to the results of threshold regression, $DR = 47.23$ was determined as a critical threshold for the level of debt, and above this threshold, the negative impact of debt on ROA may increase. The results of the study justify the need to strengthen debt monitoring in state-owned enterprises, stabilize profitability, optimize operating costs, and pre-estimate fiscal risks.*

Keywords: *state-owned enterprises, financial stability, debt level, ROA, FS index, threshold regression, Newey–West model, fiscal risks.*

Introduction. Ensuring the effective operation of state-owned commercial enterprises, their implementation of activities based on market principles and increasing the ability to make independent decisions based on investment opportunities is of urgent importance for the macroeconomic stability of the country. When such enterprises are financially optimally managed, the cost structure is effectively formed, the potential of human resources increases, and the ability to produce quality products and services based on modern technologies expands. At the same time, a decrease in the level of profitability of state-owned enterprises, higher operating costs than revenues, and a lack of investment resources can create additional fiscal pressure and macro-fiscal risks for the state budget. For this reason, scientific research such as studying the capital structure of enterprises with a state share and assessing their financial stability is of urgent importance.

Literature review. In order to increase the efficiency of the activities of large state-owned enterprises and commercial banks and accelerate the attraction of foreign investment through their privatization, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PQ-145 dated April 21, 2025 “On the privatization of large state-owned enterprises in international markets” was adopted. It is also planned to list the shares of 12 large state-owned enterprises on stock exchanges through IPO and SPO from 2026. Ensuring the financial stability of these enterprises is of great importance in implementing these processes.

Financial indicators As a dependent variable, five financial ratios were studied in the studies of Haron et al. (2009) and Assagaf and Gunawan (2017), and this approach allows dividing financial indicators into the following categories: financial indicators with high levels of performance or not bankrupt, financial indicators in the gray zone, and weak financial indicators or in a state of bankruptcy.

Abor (2005) stated in his study that capital structure is measured by the ratio of total debt to equity. According to the study, it has a significant negative impact on profitability in enterprises.

That is, the use of debt can reduce the level of profitability, so the choice of financing is made by prioritizing the use of capital or selling shares in the stock market.

In the studies of Schreiner (1997), government subsidies stimulate the growth of the national economy through state-owned enterprises as a driving force in industrial growth, business development and other areas that are beneficial to the socio-economic society as a whole, namely the development of education, health services and increasing the welfare of society in general. Subsidies are used by society and affect economic growth, because electricity prices are cheap for society, fuel prices are relatively cheap, and railway freight rates are cheap for society. In the subsidy policy, the price charged by state-owned enterprises is much lower than the cost of sales and leads to losses, so the government should establish a fund to support state-owned enterprises in the form of subsidies or additional capital.

SOEs engaged in commercial activities can pose a high level of financial risks to the state budget. These risks, referred to as fiscal risks, are factors that can cause financial results to deviate from expectations or forecasts. Financial risks of SOEs can arise from lower-than-expected dividends, taxes, high subsidies, non-repayment of loans, and the need to service guarantees on borrowing (Bova et al., 2016).

Research by Jensen and Meckling (1976) identified a potential conflict between shareholders and managers that leads to increased agency costs. A large literature has been developed on the theoretical explanation of agency costs in the capital structure, such as Myers (1984). Some studies have included debt in the capital structure in terms of the tax benefits of debt.

Zeitun and Tian (2007) found that financial leverage is negatively related to market performance and accounting performance, but one of the market performance variables, PE ratio, has a negligible effect, while the other variables of the study were Tobin's Q, market value of equity to book value ratio, ROE, ROA. Another similar study on Egypt was conducted by Ebaid (2009), who empirically investigated the effect of capital structure choice on firm performance. In his study, he used multiple regression analysis to assess the relationship between leverage level and firm performance.

Their findings also show that short-term debt, long-term debt are positively related to total assets and profitability, and total debt in the manufacturing industry is positively related to total assets and profitability. Ting and Lean (2011) studied the cross-sectional variation in credit leverage between government-listed and non-government-owned companies in Malaysia. Their study used balanced panel data using multivariate regression as the analysis method. The results show that government-owned companies consistently have higher credit leverage than non-government-owned companies. The findings show a significant positive relationship between debt ratio and tangible assets, but a negative relationship between debt ratio and profitability for both government-owned and non-government-owned companies.

Methodology. In assessing the financial stability of state-owned enterprises and developing recommendations, the financial and economic indicators of the Regional Electric Networks of the Republic of Uzbekistan were effectively used. In the analysis, we plan to develop a financial stability index using the calculation methodology. In this case:

$$FS=LQ_{norm}+ROA_{norm}+SIZE_{norm}+DR_{norm}/4$$

Standardized indicators of financial stability are used to take into account indicators such as liquidity and return on assets, changes in the company's assets, and debt level. The financial stability index is calculated using the average value of these indicators. Since DR is a negative indicator, it is inversely normalized. In the study, a dynamic time series regression model was used

to assess the lagged impact of the debt level on the financial results of the company. Return on assets - ROA was selected as the dependent variable in the model. The lagged value of ROA for one period and the lagged value of the debt level for one period were included as independent variables. This approach allows us to determine the impact of the financial position of the previous period on the current financial results.

$$ROA_t = \alpha + \rho ROA_{t-1} + \beta_1 DR_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

$$ROA_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DR_t + \beta_2 LQ_t + \beta_3 SIZE_t + \beta_4 High_t + \beta_5 (DR_t \times High_t) + \varepsilon_t$$

In assessing the financial stability of state-owned enterprises, the analysis of the relationship between financial indicators such as liquidity, debt, profitability, and enterprise size is of great scientific and practical importance. In this study, the relationship between the financial stability index, return on assets, liquidity level, debt ratio, and enterprise size of the enterprise was assessed based on 28 quarterly observations of the Regional Electric Networks JSC from the 2nd quarter of 2019 to the 1st quarter of 2026.

Analysis and results

Regional Electric Networks JSC is engaged in the sale of electricity throughout the territory of the Republic. The state plays an important role as the main shareholder, and the relevant Ministry of Energy and the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan actively participate in the management.

Table-1. Dynamic changes in the financial performance of Regional Electric Grids JSC

Indicators	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Net profit (bn, soums)	233,6	34,06	400,35	-56,68	-1015,1	-472
Net income (bn, soums)	0	0	5,51	424,9	29321	0
Total assets (trln, soums)	5,99	14,25	16,47	17,04	27,7	13,11
Total liabilities (trln, soums)	1,81	5,82	7,54	8,36	17,85	20,45

Since its establishment, the assets and liabilities of the Regional Electric Grids JSC have shown a growing trend. As of 2024, its total assets amounted to 13.11 trillion soums, while its total liabilities amounted to 20.45 trillion soums. Its liabilities are much higher than its share assets. That is, it shows that there are 0.65 units of assets per unit of liability. The financial instability of this enterprise can create macro-fiscal risks for the state budget. Also, the financial stability of this joint-stock company increases its investment attractiveness and serves as an important factor in sustainable economic development. At the same time, we calculate the stability coefficient based on the results of the financial activities of the Regional Electric Grids JSC and determine the threshold amounts for debt based on econometric analysis. The financial condition of the enterprise was generally volatile in the period 2019q2–2026q1. The LQ indicator was 72.67 in 2019q2, and by 2026q1 it reached 183.49, which indicates an increase in the level of liquidity. At the same time, the DR also increased from 4.91 to 66.07, which means that the debt burden has increased significantly.

The ROA indicator is not stable: in some periods it was positive, for example, 6.00 in 2025q4, and in some periods it was negative, for example, -3.66 in 2023q4. The SIZE indicator increased from 8.25 to 10.53, indicating an expansion in the volume of the enterprise's assets. The financial stability index FS was 0.4239 in 2019q2 and reached 0.5936 in 2026q1. This means that the company's liquidity and asset volume have increased, but the increase in debt to 66.07 and the instability of profitability remain the main financial risk factors.

Table 2. Results of the Trent model of the financial stability indicator

FS	C	St.	t	p	[95	Int	
	oef.	Err.	-value	-value	% Conf	erval]	ig
t	.06	.02	.92	2.007	.002	1	.0**
Constant	.392	.24	6.34	1.0	.343	42	.4**
Mean dependent var	0.481		SD dependent var		0.084		
Number of obs	28		F-test		8.555		

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

The model formed as a result of econometric analysis:

$$FS = 0.3925 + 0.0061 * t$$

According to the result, the coefficient of the t variable is 0.006. This means that when time increases by one period, that is, in each quarter, FS increases by an average of 0.0061 units. The p-value of the t coefficient is 0.007, which is less than 0.01. Therefore, the effect of the time factor on FS is reliable at the 1 percent statistical significance level. In other words, the increase in the financial stability index is not random, but has a statistically based positive trend.

The overall significance of the model is also positive, $\text{Prob} > F = 0.0071$. That is, this model is statistically significant. Since the Newey-West standard errors were used, the risk of autocorrelation and heteroskedasticity was partially taken into account in the results.

We also determine the threshold value of the debt level by conducting Threshold econometric analysis. The selected period allows for dynamic monitoring of the financial condition of state-owned enterprises, identification of the critical debt threshold, and assessment of the trend of financial stability over time. This issue is of particular scientific relevance, especially since an increase in the level of debt in state-owned enterprises can affect not only the profitability of the enterprise, but also the state budget and macro-fiscal stability.

In the next stage of the study, the assumption that the impact of debt on profitability is not linear, but may change after a certain threshold point, was tested using the threshold regression approach. According to the results of the threshold analysis, the optimal threshold value for the debt level was determined to be $DR = 47.23$. This value was chosen as the point at which the sum of the squares of the model errors — SSR — was the smallest. As a result, 12 observations were separated into the low-debt group with $DR \leq 47.23$, and 16 observations into the high-debt group with $DR > 47.23$. This approach allows us to test whether the impact of debt on profitability can be differentiated in low and high-debt conditions.

In the low-debt mode, i.e. $DR \leq 47.23$:

$$ROA = 2.2542 + 0.0165DR + 0.0184LQ - 0.3186SIZE$$

In the high-debt mode, i.e. $DR > 47.23$:

$$ROA = 3.7131 - 0.0514DR + 0.0184LQ - 0.3186SIZE$$

The threshold regression model is based on the following economic logic: up to a certain limit, the level of debt can serve to finance the activities of the enterprise and expand the asset base, but after this limit is exceeded, there is a possibility that debt service costs, interest payments and financial pressure will become a factor that reduces profitability. For this purpose, a dummy variable called high was introduced into the model. This variable takes the value 1 when $DR >$

47.23, and the value 0 otherwise. The additional effect of debt on profitability in the high debt regime was also estimated using the interaction variable DR_high. According to the results of the threshold regression, estimated based on the Newey–West standard errors, the overall statistical significance of the model is not strong enough. The value of Prob > F = 0.2632 for the model is greater than 0.05, which indicates that this model is not statistically reliable at the 5 percent significance level in general. The p-values of the DR, LQ, SIZE, high and DR_high variables for individual coefficients were above 0.05.

To determine the overall impact of DR in conditions of high debt, the “lincom DR + DR_high” test was performed. According to the results, the overall impact of debt on ROA in periods when DR > 47.23 was -0.0514. This is an economically significant result, which means that negative pressure on profitability may increase after debt exceeds the specified limit. However, since the p-value of this effect is equal to 0.056, it can be considered statistically reliable.

The results of the analysis show that the financial stability index of the state-owned enterprise had a positive growth trend during the studied period. However, this positive trend was accompanied by an increase in the debt burden and instability of profitability. Threshold analysis identified a potential critical threshold for debt levels of 47.23. Above this threshold, the impact of debt on profitability becomes negative. However, the results suggest that optimizing debt levels, improving cost efficiency, and stabilizing profitability are key areas for strengthening financial stability in state-owned enterprises.

Conclusion. The results of the study showed a positive growth trend in the financial stability of the Regional Electric Networks JSC. According to the Newey–West model, the financial stability (FS) indicator increased by an average of 0.006 units per quarter, and this result is statistically significant. This indicates that the liquidity and assets of the enterprise are increasing. However, along with the positive trend, the level of debt has also increased significantly. The DR indicator has increased from 4.91 to 66.07, which indicates that the financial risks of the enterprise are increasing. The fact that the ROA indicator has a negative value in some periods indicates that profitability is not stable.

According to the results of the threshold regression, the value of 47.23 for the level of debt was determined as a possible critical threshold. In periods above this threshold, the effect of debt on ROA shifts to the negative side. That is, as debt increases, negative pressure on the profitability of the enterprise may increase. Although the financial stability index of the enterprise is increasing, the increase in debt burden and instability of profitability remain the main risk factors. Therefore, when assessing financial stability in state-owned enterprises, it is necessary to conduct a comprehensive analysis of debt, profitability and fiscal risks, along with liquidity and asset volume.

For this reason, it is necessary to strengthen the system of constant monitoring of the level of debt in state-owned enterprises. In particular, it is advisable to evaluate cases above the value of DR = 47.23 as a signal of financial risk. It is also advisable to use a comprehensive index approach when assessing financial stability. In addition, to increase the profitability of the enterprise, it is necessary to reduce operating costs, reduce technological losses and digitize management processes. As a result of the study, in order to strengthen financial stability in the Regional Electric Networks JSC, it is necessary to optimize debt, increase profitability, optimize costs and pre-assess fiscal risks.

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